

The Need to Activate Enterprises for the Issue of Securities and Ensuring Reliable Liquid Financial Instruments

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Abstract: *The article, based on practical materials, presents the importance and priority of the development of the stock market, notes that to ensure the development of the stock market, qualified financial intermediaries are required in the form of various investment funds that would contribute to more effective accumulation of individuals' money and their investments in securities market instruments. Specific proposals are given to ensure the volume of transactions on the stock market.*

Keywords: *financial segment, stimulation, stock market, personal savings, shortage of financial instruments, investor, protection, competent intermediary.*

At present, favorable conditions are being created for the creation and development of investment funds. This was due to the additional incentives adopted to ensure the development of the stock market. In many countries, networks of financial intermediaries have been created, since few people themselves can directly buy shares of companies on the stock exchanges; in most cases, they can turn to competent market intermediaries. This procedure effectively operates in all industrially developed countries of the world. As for the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it can be noted that they are not sufficiently informed and are interested in the new market of opportunities to increase capital. And right now we need qualified financial intermediaries in the form of various investment funds that could more effectively accumulate the money of individuals and invest them in securities market instruments.

In fairness, it should be noted that the key moment for the development of the securities market (SM) should be steadily developing and profitable enterprises (companies) that would become investment objects. The development of enterprises is the main task of government policy and the implementation of a set of measures to protect local producers and stimulate import-substituting production.

The priority of developing the stock market in Uzbekistan did not arise by chance. Today, it can be noted with confidence that the most developed financial segment is the banking one. In recent years, certain results have been achieved in the development of the domestic RCB. If we analyze the activities of the national organizer of trades, we will see that since 2022, the volume of transactions has increased (Fig. 1):

- with foreign currency – 3.1 times;
- with government securities – 22 times;
- with non-government securities – almost 70 times.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of transaction volumes on the Tashkent Stock Exchange for 2017-2021

In relative terms, the total turnover of the TFB amounted to 110% of GDP at the beginning of 2023 (at the beginning of 2017 - 22%). As for the structure of trading sectors, the main feature of the domestic stock market is visible here, associated with the predominance of institutional investors of a conservative type in the market. Transactions with government securities account for up to 70% of the TFB turnover, transactions in the foreign currency sector - up to 12%. In the sector of securities of international financial organizations (CB IFO) and bills of exchange, trading is practically absent.

The main problems arising from the structure of transactions on the TSE are the shortage of financial instruments with a certain reliability. Another problem of the stock market development is connected with the activities of issuers – the introduction of corporate management in companies, the transition to IFRS. The third, key problem, connected with the first two, is the incompatibility within the framework of legislative requirements for nominal holding.

From the above factors it should be noted that the most realistic investment object for domestic investors are Russian securities.

For the successful functioning of the stock market in Uzbekistan, it is necessary, first of all, to work on the policy of development and expansion of the activities of joint-stock companies (JSC); improvement of the legislation of the stock market (SM); relying on the practice of development of SM in advanced countries, to apply various financial instruments by conducting a certain policy of attracting savings of both legal entities and individuals for the development and expansion of the stock market in the country.

At the present time, it is necessary to intensify the preparation of enterprises for the issue of shares and corporate bonds, thereby expanding the list of reliable liquid financial instruments offered on the financial market.

In order to attract the widest possible range of participants to the securities market, and especially to interest an important part of the stock market – the population of the country, and to involve it in the capital market, which must be made the most reliable and highly profitable investment of capital, in our opinion, it is necessary:

- fully revise all draft laws on the securities market;
- do not be afraid to experiment and adopt the experience of developed countries along with their huge range of stock market instruments;

- conduct large-scale advertising campaigns to disclose the concept of the RCB, its instruments and the need to join it. And do this in an accessible, attractive and understandable language for all citizens of our republic through mass media, seminars, conferences, round tables, and widely distributed courses;
- to give everyone the opportunity to understand the essence and enormous importance of the stock market as a tool for the potential increase of personal savings;
- create favorable and acceptable conditions for investment funds, as their role is great in accumulating private capital of the population and involving our compatriots in this interesting and exciting world of securities. This is only one part of the events that should be carried out on our stock market for its fruitful existence and for achieving world standards.

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